

Anton Paar Kaomi for Nova

version 1.01
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Report date: 09/04/2025 **Operator:** admin
File Name: AA_TB-DMAP pag 156_CO2 273K.qcuPhysIso

Analysis Information

Sample	ID AA_TB-DMAP pag	Weight 0.1g	Description AA_TB-DMAP pag 156_CO2
Analysis	Data ID {4ff56029-24ac-4ee4-a2d4-5da267cf5686}	Date 2022/05/09	Duration 0.00min
	Operator quantachrome		Firmware 0.00
	Instrument NOVA	Station ID A	Cell ID 79
	Ambient Temp. -273.16°C	p₀ Mode Calculate	Thermal Delay 600sec
	Cell Volume 0		
Adsorbate	Name Carbon-dioxide	Molecular Weight 0g/mol	Cross Sectional Area 0Å ² /molecule
	Non-Ideality 0 _{1/Torr}	Bath Temperature 273.15K	
Degassing	Degas Time 0.0hrs	Degas Temperature 0.0°C	

Data Reduction Parameters

Thermal Transpiration	yes	Eff. Molec. Diameter	3.54Å
Eff. Cell Diameter	4mm		
Adsorbate Model	Name Carbon Dioxide	Molecular Weight 44.0095g/mol	Cross Sectional Area 21Å ² /molecule
	Bath Temperature 273.15K		

BET Multipoint BET Results

Isotherm Branch	Adsorption
Slope	12.8953
Intercept	0.289349
Correlation coeff., r	0.999931
C constant	45.5665
Surface area	217.946 m ² /g

Table - BET Multipoint BET

Relative Pressure, p/p ₀	Volume Adsorbed @STP cm ³ /g	1 / [W((p ₀ /p) - 1)]
0.0254583	21.5567	0.6172
0.0264567	21.9450	0.6307
0.027431	22.3288	0.6433
0.0283462	22.6799	0.6551
0.0292884	23.0304	0.6672
0.0301574	23.3494	0.6782
0.0308652	23.6108	0.6870